

Assessing Courses of the Online Learning Agreement

ToT 'How to use the AsCOLA evaluation tool'

Outline

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Learning objectives

After this training, the participant is able to...

- Explain the importance of exchange student evaluations.
- Explore the use of the AsCOLA tool.
- Examine ways to utilize results to improve courses and student satisfaction.
- Learn strategies to engage others with the tool.

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Outline of training

In the table below the outline of the training can be found.

Time	Topic	Goal	What/how (incl. slides)	Activities
10 min.	Welcome and introduction	Short introduction to the training, icebreaker activities to get to know the participants.	Welcome the participants, walk them through the outline of the training and share with them the learning objectives (what will they be able to know/do after the training?). Explain about the project of AsCOLA and share the disclaimers of the tool. Explain to them what the topics of the evaluation survey are.	Icebreaker activity: <i>think-pair-share</i> ("What do you think is the most impactful outcome of student evaluations?")
10 min.	Understanding the importance of student evaluations	Explain the value of exchange student feedback in improving course quality and enhancing the exchange experience.	Explain the importance of evaluating with the use of the slides. There are 4 main reasons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refining course quality • Addressing learning needs • Feedback culture / continuous improvement • Improved mobility experience 	
20 min.	Demonstration of the tool	Demonstrate the process for students filling out evaluations and staff reviewing results.	Walk through the essentials of the students experience and the HEI experience. See the two rows below for further explanations of both sides of the tool and what to explain to participants. Use printed versions of the 'How to use the tool' guides for both students and HEIs, or send digital versions beforehand. Note: The slides show screenshots of the tool. However, it is recommended to walk through	

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			the tool 'live' instead of showing screenshots. If not possible, use the slides.	
10 min.	BREAK			
20 min.	How to use evaluation results effectively	Design strategies for improving course quality based on feedback. Encourage other stakeholders to engage with the tool.	Summarize the guide 'How to use results'. Share a printed version of the guide with participants <i>or</i> send it to them beforehand digitally. Additionally, explain how to engage all relevant stakeholders in order to maximize the success of the evaluation tool. Summarize from the infographic on 'Engaging all stakeholders', hand it printed to the participants <i>or</i> send it to them digitally.	Optional activity: Let participants write down all their ideas on how to engage stakeholders. Let participants discuss their answers in pairs.
25 min.	Try-out	To make the training impactful, it is essential to let participants try-out the tool themselves.	These aspects are particularly important to focus on during the try-out: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to log in on the HEI side • How to browse through courses • How to select a course to view • How to walk through the results <p>In case of live training, walk around and answer questions from participants as they practice.</p> <p>In case of online training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask participants to virtually raise their hand when having questions; • Let them share questions in chat; 	

			Or divide the participants in breakout rooms where they can help out each other.	
5 min.	Wrap-up		Wrap-up the training by summarizing and sharing what's next (and include contact details). Check if there are any remaining questions.	

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